

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations

Annual Short Course

Special Session on University Transportation Infrastructure

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Examination of Segmental Liner Loading for Soft Ground Tunnels: Design Approaches vs. Actual Behavior

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Design Approaches

1. Analytical solutions
2. 2D plain strain numerical analysis
3. 3D numerical analysis

Analytical solutions

3D FEM/FDM

2D FEM/FDM

Design Assumptions

1. Segmental lining joints
2. Ground behavior- Elastic or Elasto-plastic
3. Tunnel pre-convergence
4. Construction process staging
5. More ...

Segmental joints

Soil behavior

CD Test
on Clay
or Sand
 $c' \geq 0$
 $\phi' > 0$

LDP

u – tunnel pre-convergence

Tunnel Pre-convergence

Two main excavation procedures for modeling the tunnel excavation and support installation

- The “wished into place method”
 - No relaxation is considered
- Convergence-Confinement Method (CCM)
 - 3D effects of the excavation face

Longitudinal Displacement Profile

- Existing LDP equations based on elastic or elastic perfectly-plastic ground for unsupported tunnels- No research on the influence of non-linear stiffness and internal TBM pressure

Construction Process Assumptions

EPB/slurry TBM tunneling

- Shield ground interface
- Face/chamber/shield annulus pressure
- Grout injection and time dependent hardening

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- 5.6 km of twin bored tunnels
- 23 cross passages
- Main tunnels:
 - Excavation diameter 6.64 m
 - Shield diameter 6.44 m 10 cm gap between shield and excavation
 - Segmental lining th=25 cm, OD 6.25 m
 - Distance between tunnel axis 12.2 m

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Geology:

- Complex and highly variable interlayered glacial soil deposits
- Groundwater pressure at Tunnel invert between 0 to 3 bars

□ $0.6 < K_0 < 3$

Field measurements

Instrumentation and monitoring-Strain gauges

- Vibrating wire strain gauges rings at 17 cross passage location
- At cross section 1- two rings were instrumented
- Three segments of each selected ring were instrumented
- In each segment 2 strain gauges

Field measurements

Strain gauges

2D Numerical Modeling

- FLAC 3D finite difference software
- Liner elements
- Joint behavior – rotational stiffness
- Time dependent grout stiffness
- Hardening soil constitutive model
- Modeled both wished into place (zero pre-convergence) and an estimate using CCM

Wished into place

CCM

Cross section 1

Results: Model Prediction in Tunnel 1

Moment (kN-m/m)

Thrust (kN/m) Wished into Place

Cross section 1

Results: Model Prediction in Tunnel 1

Moment (kN-m/m)

Thrust (kN/m)

Wished into Place
after 2nd tunnel
excavated

Cross section 1

Results: Model Prediction in Tunnel 2

Moment (kN-m/m)

Thrust (kN/m)

Wished into Place

Findings

2D analysis

- Wished into place analysis over-estimates the thrust forces; that actual thrust force is 30-50% less
- Actual low thrust forces, result in unconservative N-M capacity envelope when using wished into place analysis

- ACI 318.11 Code
- No preconvergence
- 2D FE CCM
- ◆ Measurements

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Pressure monitoring

- Face pressure
- Shield annulus pressure
- Grout injection pressure

3D Numerical Modeling process

The step by step excavation process includes:

- a. total muck pressure at the excavation chamber
- b. simplification of the shield by annulus shield pressure
- c. segmental lining support system
- d. annulus grout pressure
- e. two component grout time-dependent stiffness

Results – First tunnel

Liner loads in first tunnel

Results – Second tunnel

Liner loads in second tunnel

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Face pressure monitoring:

- Before monitored segment installation 2 pressure drops occur

Results – Pressure drop

Ring thrust force comparison due to TBM pressure drop

(a) Second tunnel
Moment (kN-m/m)

(b) Second tunnel
Thrust (kN/m)

— FLAC3D Ring A ◆ Measurements Ring A
— FLAC3D Ring B ◆ Measurements Ring B
- - FLAC3D Ring A no pressure drop

Findings

3D analysis

- Drops of the chamber pressure result in a significant influence on tunnel lining loads
- For pressure balance TBMs with the flow of pressurized material behind the shield into the shield annulus, the final lining loads are controlled by the chamber pressure

Thank You! Questions?

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